

PHARMACOLOGICAL AUDIT - A TOOL FOR THE RATIONAL USE OF MEDICINES

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Abstract. *It is necessary to unify the optimal modes of the diagnostic and treatment process from the standpoint of introducing standards (protocols) approved by evidence-based medicine. When conducting a clinical and pharmacological audit of 411 medical records from the departments of neonatology, emergency pediatrics and pediatric intensive care, the most common types of irrational use of drugs were identified:*

- simultaneous use of too many drugs in one patient (polypharmacy);
- inappropriate use of antimicrobial drugs, often in inadequate doses.

An analysis of the use of the 50 most commonly used medicines in Uzbekistan shows that many of them are either ineffective or not safe enough.

Keywords: *clinical and pharmacological audit, treatment effectiveness, rational use of medicines, drug safety.*

Relevance. In order to increase the effectiveness of treatment at the modern, complex, market stage of the formation of the state system of protecting citizens, it is necessary to systematize approaches to the tactics of patient management. It is necessary to unify the optimal modes of the diagnostic and treatment process from the standpoint of introducing standards (protocols) approved by evidence-based medicine. Certification and licensing of medical activities must be carried out through organizational, preventive, diagnostic, therapeutic and rehabilitation standards (protocols). We need a unified, national, standard approach of health authorities and institutions to the International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD X revision). Performers must be aware of accepted medical standards. Ignorance of medical standards is not an excuse for insufficient treatment or inaction of a doctor. To ensure adequate therapy, consultations are needed to justify the advisability of using certain diagnostic and treatment methods to ensure the quality of the diagnostic and treatment process at the modern level.

Standards are a guaranteed list of organizational, diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive actions to be performed in the process of providing medical services. Standards are introduced with the aim of unifying the requirements that medical and preventive care must meet.

Rational use of drugs is the use of drugs in which patients receive drugs according to clinical need, in doses that meet individual needs, for an adequate period of time.

The purpose of the study is to identify the irrational use of drugs.

Materials and methods. To improve the quality of treatment, rational choice and use of medications, as well as to exclude polypharmacy, an audit of 411 medical records of the departments of neonatology, emergency pediatrics and pediatric intensive care of Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care was conducted.

Regional, or irrational use of medicines is the use of medicines not in accordance with the above definition of rational use. Globally, more than 50% of drugs are prescribed, dispensed or

sold incorrectly, and 50% of patients do not take them properly. Moreover, a third of the world's population does not have access to necessary drugs. The most common types of irrational drug use include: - simultaneous use of too many drugs in one patient (polypharmacy); - inadequate use of antimicrobials, often in inadequate doses, for non-bacterial infections; - excessive use of injections in cases where oral forms of drugs would be more appropriate; - administration is not in accordance with clinical guidelines; - improper use of drugs during self-medication, often with drugs that are exclusively prescription drugs. Lack of access to medicines and the use of medicines in inadequate dosages lead to an increase in morbidity and mortality, especially in cases of childhood infections and chronic diseases, in particular hypertension, diabetes, epilepsy and mental disorders. Inadequate and excessive use of drugs leads to unjustified additional costs (often the money of the patients themselves), as well as significant damage to the health of patients (adverse treatment outcomes and the development of adverse reactions to drugs). Excessive use of antibiotics increases the resistance of microorganisms, promotes the natural selection of polyresistant strains. Injections in non-sterile conditions are a factor in the spread of hepatitis, HIV/AIDS and other blood-borne diseases. Resistance to antibacterial agents has become a global problem, seriously affecting health care in developed and developing countries. This is a consequence of the widespread and incorrect use of antibacterial agents. One of the illustrative examples of this kind is the inclusion of antibiotics in combination preparations for the treatment of patients with diarrhea and influenza, when antibiotics, sulfa drugs and other drugs that have virtually no effect on viruses are prescribed. This is an unwise, dangerous and useless practice. The data of many researchers confirm the international nature of the problem of misuse of medicines (drugs). Hundreds of millions of dollars are wasted every year due to the misuse of medicines. An analysis of the use of the 50 most commonly used medicines in Uzbekistan shows that 40% of them are either ineffective or insufficiently safe.

Research results. Medical errors when prescribing medications can be divided into groups: Incompatibility of prescribed medications. Sometimes doctors prescribe several drugs that, when taken together, enhance, weaken, or neutralize each other's effects. For example: - co-administration of diclofenac with diazepam leads to a weakening of the effect of diclofenac. - acyclovir prescribed together with aminophylline increases the concentration of aminophylline in the blood plasma. - simultaneous administration of cimetidine erythromycin with diazepam delays the metabolism of diazepam.

Violation of the integrity of the dosage form. Doctors often prescribe medications in fractions: half, a third, a quarter, and even one-eighth of a tablet. In such cases, it is difficult to predict what dose the patient will receive. One of the biggest problems for doctors is prescribing enzyme (festal, mezim-forte, pancreatin) and iron-containing drugs (sorbifer, ferroplex) to children. Since these drugs are coated with a protective shell that is soluble only in the intestine, a violation of its integrity leads to the destruction of the drug in the stomach and, consequently, lack of effect. In such cases, it is more advisable to prescribe iron supplements in the form of syrups or drops. There are cases when the doctor prescribes half a capsule of acyclovir, amoxicillin and recommends that patients open the capsule and divide its contents before taking it. At the same time, the doctor must remember that if the drug is released in a protective capsule, its destruction is unacceptable and is fraught with adverse consequences for the patient.

Duplication. Doctors prescribe two drugs from the same group and the same pharmacological group at the same time. Most often this occurs when a new drug is prescribed

together with previously known ones. One gets the impression that the doctor needs some kind of insurance to achieve a therapeutic effect. In fact, there is an undesirable increase in the effect of the prescribed drugs. A good example is the simultaneous administration of diclofenac with nimesulide, metoprolol with atenolol, Enap with diroton, diazepam with Xanax. A curious example is the simultaneous prescription of the same drug under different trade names, such as famotidine with quamatel, apaurin with Relanium, metoprolol with Egilok.

Errors in indicating drug doses. When prescribing treatment, errors are made in indicating the doses of medications. As a result, single doses can be overestimated several times. For example: - diazepam is available in doses of 5 and 10 mg. Doctors prescribe 50 mg and even 500 mg instead of 5 mg, exceeding the highest dose by 10 and 100 times. - alprazolam (Xanax) - release form 0.25 and 0.5 mg, and doctors prescribe 5 mg in prescriptions. - phenozeepam - release form 1 and 0.5 mg, and recipes contain doses of 5 mg, 10 mg. No matter how strange it may sound, errors occur when converting milligrams to grams. Simply put, doctors make mistakes about the number of zeros after the decimal point. An incorrectly placed comma increases the dose tens or hundreds of times.

Prescribing medications to children. The use in pediatric practice of drugs that are contraindicated for children or prescribed from a certain age. For example: - famotidine - prescribed to young children half or one fourth of the tablet. However, famotidine is not recommended for use under 16 years of age, as clinical studies have not been conducted, and is contraindicated in young children.

- naphthyzin - doctors prescribe it to children under one year of age, contrary to the instructions prohibiting its use for children under two years of age. Naphthyzin 0.1% is contraindicated for use in children under 18 years of age.

- Bromhexine - is prescribed in syrup for children under one year of age, although according to the instructions it is contraindicated for children under 6 years of age.

- prospan drops - prescribed to infants, despite the fact that it is contraindicated for children under one year of age.

Conclusion. According to WHO, it is possible that two thirds of all medications prescribed to children are of little value or even useless. WHO points out that inappropriate use of medicines in children has both immediate (waste of resources) and long-term (potential danger of adverse reactions) consequences. And these are strong arguments in favor of a careful approach to prescribing medications for children. Medicines can be toxic because children have a reduced metabolic rate. The blood-brain barrier, especially in infants, is more permeable to drugs, so drugs can primarily affect the immature central nervous system. The liver and kidneys are still in the development stage, and medications are slowly excreted from the body. When regularly receiving information about new medicines, it is necessary to remember that the newest and most expensive medicine will not necessarily be the safest, and the costs will be effective. Medications reinforce the focus on pharmacotherapy, but most pediatric problems can be easily prevented through vaccination programs, proper nutrition, access to clean water and the environment. If drugs are used incorrectly, there may be a risk of toxicity and resistance. As a result of irrational prescribing, the doctor becomes defenseless against claims from patients, criticism from colleagues and pressure from pharmaceutical companies.

Thus, patients often spend a lot of money on useless, sometimes low-quality, and sometimes simply dangerous medicines. Pharmacotherapy based on full knowledge of medicines

and the patient, providing for the use of medicines with maximum benefit to the patient and with minimal undesirable side effects, allows the doctor to draw a line between the main and secondary qualities of medicines, facilitates the determination of their therapeutic value.

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